

REDUCTION OF LOSSES DURING HARVESTING AND STORAGE OF POTATO PRODUCTS

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Abstract: *The article outlines the optimal options for quality storage and product placement, from the acceptance of potato products to the delivery process. The factors that lead to natural losses and decomposition during cargo storage are identified and eliminated. In addition, the process of storing and delivering products is analyzed and proposals for addressing deficiencies in the existing logistics network are developed.*

Key words: food warehouse, storage mode, cooling system, cargo storage, types of transport, storage in container, cargo placement, cargo handling, logistics network.

Currently, vegetables and melon products are consumed in the country, while potatoes are considered a tour product. The country also consumes products resulting from the processing of potato fairs. Diced potatoes, diced 0.9x0.9x0.9 m and about 450 kg in a cooking container. Currently, the container size is 0.8 x 1.2 m. Bundan weighs about 30 kg, and also not only in bundalanilapta. He is known for his Yiddish sizes and Yang hillarines yaratish, jumladan, polymer materials developed in Ishlar by Olib Borilgan. Yiddishlars build basic buildings using all models of turlars with convenient placement and a lifting height of 3.5-5 m to ensure a secure fit [1].

With a natural wind, the potatoes are rolled in the greenhouse. Bundai uyumlarning is catapulted by 3x3-6x6 m catapults and Undan catapults with a lifting capacity of 10-30 tons. The maximum lifting height is 1.8-2 m. The

maximum lifting height is 40-45% of the maximum lifting length.

In addition, the population of the country supplies potatoes as a needy area in the amount of 500 thousand tons. The main directions of potato growing: Poland, Russia, Belarus, the Celtic countries.

In this verse, Allah Almighty told about what happened on Mount Sinai when the Prophet Muhammad (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) went to Medina. For example, the temperature rises after 4 °C, 3-6 milligrams of gaseous carbonate anhydride circulate for each kilogram. In the last round, Esa tunganaklar met with boshlab, breathed more air, and the Undan bridge collapsed.

Potato growing is an important feature of the Issyklik and namlikni uncha Cope ajratmaidi vegetable growing. It is necessary to use soglom and saralangan potatoes (naturally ventilated) 1.5 m gacha and actively ventilated 3.5-4 m Gacha kalinlikda roof [2].

During the study, an analysis of the harvest of tubers, parts of the machine and flask of olinib, saralangan potatoes was carried out. Potatoes are peeled and grated. Potato seeds every year 2-4 August 3-5 October. Each verse was revealed as an example. Potato processing plant: meat grinder, KVN-2 machine and K-3 combine harvester, both cut breasts.

1- picture. French fries with a high fiber content

When harvesting potatoes in a combine, the infection rate is 27.7%, when

harvesting potatoes-4.5%, when harvesting potatoes infected by a machine - 10%. In particular, ventilation holes are installed on KVN—2 machines and combines equipped with air vents and air vents. In chambers equipped with ventilation, the air temperature is 3.2—5.5 ° C, in rooms with natural ventilation-19.2-31 ° C. The natural loss of potatoes stored in warehouses was -2.9% when stored in machines and 3.1—3.5% when stored in machines.

The results of storing potatoes in natural ventilated or non-cooled warehouses are somewhat different. In this case, the moisture content of potatoes disappeared more than 2.5 times. It accounted for 7.2 percent on hand-rolled potatoes, 8 percent on special cars when rolled, and 8.89 percent on combine harvesters. On the potatoes in the storage, the tinim period accelerated, his eyes woke up, and the tubers began to grow. The total output of hand-sawn potatoes was twice as much as in an artificially cooled warehouse as in an orthicrock, while that of machine-sawn potatoes was three times as much. The output of potatoes sorted by mechanisms from storage for two months increased by an average of 5 percent compared to that sorted by hand. Thus, when roasting by means of mechanisms, the amount of potatoes with damaged peel and flesh increases. After mining with KVN — 2 machines, the potatoes sorted on the KSP — 15 machine are more damaged than when assembled with a combine harvester.

In conclusion, in the mechanization method, potatoes harvested in the summer should be stored in an artificially cooled warehouse. In this case, up to 0.8 percent of the output from the carded potatoes in the KVN — 2 machine, up to 2.8 percent from the carted in the combine. The waste of potatoes goes away at the expense of the expenses saved during roasting. Experimentally, it was anicized that harvesting and sorting machines severely damaged potato tubers, which had not yet been improved constructively. In order to somehow soften the punching of potatoes, it was determined that part of the working organs of the machines should be covered with rubber, and the quality of work of these machines was also collected, as well as a lot of data on the decrease and rotting of potato weight during storage [3].

The leaves of the lorx variety potato were harvested on the second, seventh, eleventh and fourteenth day with a KGP — 2 branded combine harvester. It turns out that the longer the Leaf is taken from the day of mowing, the less the potatoes will be damaged. For example, on Day 14, potatoes were 72 percent undamaged when they were harvested, 21 percent were partially damaged, and 7 percent were heavily damaged. So, first mowing and then harvesting potato leaves will allow the soil to dry out, which in turn will speed up the yield of the crop. Excess moisture in the potato stalks evaporates, the legume flakes solidify and become less damaged during harvesting. In terms of quality, there is a difference in the total yield when picking potatoes in a combine, a cutter and a lake. It can be seen that healthy tubers turned out to be 83 percent when the potatoes were manually roasted, 59 percent when they were roasted in a KVN— 2 machine, and even less (44 percent) when they were roasted in a combine. The amount of potatoes partially heavily damaged by manual roasting was also only 17 percent, and when machine roasting was more 41-56 percent.

When storing potatoes, the temperature of the warehouse is reduced, and overnight cooling is achieved gradually at 0.5-1.0°C.

For the preparation of heaps when storing potatoes, hilly plots are usually chosen, in which the water of sizot is located deeper, well-ventilated. It is desirable that the heaps and ditches are in the shade of a plough ,low-falling, north-facing, and trees. The width of the URA is 60-70 CM, the depth is 70-80 CM, and the length can be as desired. At a distance of every 2-3 m, 30-40 cm of fences are left. In the heap, the potatoes are first dug into a trench 30 cm deep and 2 m wide. To improve air exchange, a ditch 30x30 CM in size is hollowed out in the middle, on which a wooden fence from the rafters is laid or a Dry Branch is pressed. The Spruce Head stands out from one end of the Burt, is 20x20 CM in size, and a steeply-mounted air-dragging board pipe serves to keep the warm air of the heap out. The plank pipe is joined by transverse ventilation ducts and pushed out by the ground of the heap. Caps are placed on top so that moisture does not get into the

heap through the pipe. This pipe, which draws air, is installed at an interval of 2-3 meters. It is preferable that the potatoes are placed in the wraps in the morning so that it cools down a lot all night. When the potatoes are settled, a 15-20 cm thick pod or Reed is first closed to the top of the scrolls and heaps, and then soil is pulled over it to a thickness of 30-35 CM. When autumn comes hot, the soil weighing work is carried out in two terms: first the soil is thrown out to a thickness of 15-20 cm, and then the thickness of the soil is brought to 30-45 CM when the cold begins to fall [4-6].

Heaps in khanduk are usually built with a capacity of 10-12 to 35-40 tonnes of product, ranging in size from 3-3 to 6-6 m, leaving corridors from both sides of the warehouse. The walls and base of the trench heap will have 2-3 cm slits so that air can walk. The bottom, on the other hand, should be raised 25-30 cm from the warehouse floor, and the back wall of the heap should also be kept at the same distance from the warehouse wall. A space of 10-15 cm is left between the walls of adjacent heaps. Potatoes are well stored without urination, if they are shed 1.5 m thick from January to February. For even longer storage, a layer of potatoes is spread up to 1 M, and potatoes that are mechanically damaged or without peeling are spread 0.8 m thick. On hot summer days, potatoes should be even thinner 0.3—0.4 m thick. The height of the heap also depends on its porosity. Porosity is determined by the size of the potato tubers and their partial contamination.

A month and a half before placing the product in storage, the warehouses are treated with a formalin solution. In this case, a contribution of 40 percent formalin is applied to three parts of water. For every 100-150 M², 40 liters of solution are spent in containers where potatoes are stored at the same time should also be disinfected.

Disinfection can also be done with chlorine lime. To do this, add 2-3 kg of chlorine lime to 5 -10 L of water and mix, and the building is whitewashed using a brush or sprayer. To regularly measure the temperature, thermometers with a wooden sheath are installed in the middle of the warehouse and on the sides of the

door: the first thermometer will be 160 cm above the floor, the second-30 cm. To measure relative humidity, a psychrometer is installed in the middle of the barn and in each heap. In addition, a thermometer is also placed between a pile (40 cm above the floor). To do this, an ordinary Burt thermometer in a metal sheath or an electric thermometer with the PTET—62 type is used, which allows you to measure the temperature of ten places in one lane of the heap. Temperature and relative humidity are measured twice a day: before ventilation and 30-40 minutes after completion. The temperature in the piles is measured once every two to three days, the results of which are recorded in a special journal. In warehouses, the relative humidity of the air should be 85-95 percent and the temperature should be around 2-3° [7,8].

In artificially non —cooling warehouses (sheep, Oqtepa, Keles, etc.), a layer of potato heap betida 7-25 cm deep, sometimes 60-70 cm deep between the heap, or a layer of ostki-100-120 cm deep, is damaged. Usually in the warehouse, redefined potatoes are stored for a maximum of 30-40 days. The most spending during storage will be associated with the sorting of potatoes and moving from place to place. Potatoes of the imported Lorx variety are placed in khanduk at a thickness of 1.4 m from 16 T and sorted in the third decade of February. To do this, on a pile of potatoes, one or two wooden bridges are placed, parallel to the wall of the trench.

In most cases, sweating was observed until the end of the storage period. Active ventilation initially reduced the sweating zone, and later the potatoes were completely soaked, and the excess moisture in the layer evaporated.

Figure 2. Shares of output when storing potatoes imported from domestic and abroad in storage.

In ventilated basements, potatoes were the most abundant when stored - 8.9 percent, and in radiator — cooled chambers, at least-4.7 percent waste, in a naturally-ventilated basement, 7.4 percent, and finally, in air-cooled chambers, the amount of ham chikit was much higher. Active ventilation causes the moisture of the potatoes to crumble slightly. In rotting and growing protrusions, the lumpy legality is thrown into the fall. In this case, 17.1 percent chicory was the most common in controlled warehouses, active ventilation was used, and artificial refrigerated warehouses had little potato waste. Thus, the total loss when imported potatoes were stored in basements with natural air exchange was 24.5 percent, 17.5 percent in warehouses with the same but ventilation, 10.7 percent in radiator-cooled chambers and 7.9 percent in air-cooled chambers. The use of low - temperature air at the coolest times of the day allows you to ventilate the potatoes, lower the temperature inside the warehouse to 0.5-4.5° C than in warehouses with an air exchange system. The relative humidity of the air has become the most comfortable when the chamber and warehouses with the refrigerator are cooled

with air. Cooling the chambers in the cold air medium reduced the relative humidity of the air by 9 percent optimally. In the case of artificially cooled chambers with radiators, the relative humidity of the air stood above normal. The use of active ventilation when the product is stored in non-refrigerated warehouses avoids potato moisture by 1-5 percent more than in the control. Cooled by cold air .in the cameras, too, the NAM of the potatoes avoided 1.8 percent more than in the radiator chamber. In non-cooled warehouses, when potatoes are ventilated with a regular cool air, the amount of chikits indicated in the act was reduced by twice as much as in warehouses with a ventilation system. Radiator cameras rot in chambers cooled by artificial air, and the output from the growth of potatoes decreased by three or more times. Thus, when potatoes were stored in winter, the use of active ventilation reduced the total amount of waste by 7% compared to natural ventilation warehouses. Artificial cooling as well as air-cooled cooling allows for a 13.8-16.6 percent reduction in potato waste when stored in the long term. The storage status of potatoes used for consumption is planned to store an average of 350 thousand tons of potatoes every year in order to provide the population with servitamin feed in the autumn and winter seasons. One of the main factors in the long-term preservation of potato products is its preservation in the correct temperature regime. Figure 1 shows the mode of storage of potatoes and vegetable products.

Table 1. Order of storage of products

Vegetables	Melting point (degrees Celsius)	Relative air humidity (percentage)	Retention periods (months)
Potato	2-5	90-95	5-8
White cabbage	-1-0	90-95	3-4
Early cabbage	1	90-95	2-2.5
Cauliflower	0	90-95	1-3

Carrots	0	90-95	5-8
Beets	0	90-95	3-7
Turnip	0	90-95	3-7
Radish	0	90-95	3-7
Redisca	0	90-95	1-2
Horseradish (root	-2-0	90-95	12 ae
Head onion	-1-0	80 гача	6-9
Pumpkin	3-15	70-80	3-6
Caen	0-2	80-90	3-8
Watermelon	5-15	70-80	3-6
Blue Tomato	12-15	85-90	1-1.5
Pink tomato	8-10	85-90	1 ae
Red tomato	2-6	85-90	0,5 ae
Cucumber	2-10	90-95	0,5 ae
Fresh pepper	2-8	90-95	0,5 ae
Salat	0	90-95	0,5 ae
Garlic	-1-6	80-85	5-7

Potatoes are stored mainly in old adapted ordinary warehouses and in modern refrigerated warehouses with artificial cooling. It is known that the above-planned amount of potatoes is prepared mainly at the expense of foreign extraction. Potatoes from abroad come in the form of a mixture of 2-3 different varieties when they say less.

Potatoes brought in late autumn, most are extremely wet (wet), and a certain amount of frostbite is also found in between. At the listed parties, the standard requirement in the best wagons is 95 percent, the exhaust fumes are 3.3 percent, semi — rot, those that can be molded or processed, the complete rot — 0.4 percent, the cold beat-0.1 percent and the soil mixture is 2.1 percent. There is almost a big difference in the quality of the product in the wagons. In some, potatoes come

well-preserved in road conditions, and there is little waste. In others, chitites, the soil that has begun to rot, and cold-hitting cockroaches, make up more than 32.6 percent of goho. The fact that 15-20% of potatoes, which are on the road for 10-12 days, are sick, indicates that during the period of its cultivation, roasting and transportation, the weather is unfavorable climatic conditions. Diseases caused by soil conditions develop in the wagon with an outbreak and give rot even after they are sorted out. Potatoes that have dimmed in soil conditions or in a wagon rot within 10-35 days, and a fusariosis patient is in full swing after two months of storage.

Since the quality of the potatoes to be brought is low, a large part is turned into waste during the transportation and storage period on the railway of 10-12 days, when the plans for the amount to be put for disassembly are not fulfilled, interruptions in the supply of products are occurring. In the following years, the condition and quality of potatoes brought for seed has improved a lot. Nevertheless, seed potatoes are still high in waste during the transportation and storage period. The waste from the transport period is 5-10 percent on average and the same percentage during the storage period (up to sowing). Cases of up to 15-22 percent of cases of chiquitis occur even after the potatoes in certain wagons have been sorted.

When potato tubers are stored for 7 months, depending on the amount of unsuitable potatoes that come out of it, an increase in their natural weight can be seen in the table below.

The infected tuber rot completely in 5-6 days at a level of 15-20°C. During the transportation and storage period, when the musty hairs are crushed and the bruises crack, the entire hairs are injured.

The potato crop is dimmed there from excess moisture for 10-15 days, walking on the road for 10-12 days, rotting 10-25 percent until it reaches the destination of consumers, and after being placed in storage, it becomes completely unusable in a short period of time.

Such tubers can negatively affect the Future Harvest, not leaving the ground after planting. To do this, the temperature should not drop below 2°.

Warehouses for storing potatoes differ in many ways, the most important of which are: what kind of product is intended for storage, planning, dimensions, capacity, size, features in construction, compliance with storage procedures, methods of product placement and mechanized level and economic indicators of loading and unloading operations.

In conclusion, taking into account all of the above, it is necessary to improve the technology of transportation of new products in order to extend the shelf life of the delivered products and increase their competitiveness in the foreign market, which determines the relevance of the study.

Potato product growers should be provided with empty standard containers, centrally carry out such operations as cooling, labeling, packaging of products, the formation of packages and large transport batches from them, as well as the mechanization of cargo unloading operas.

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